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Open Science NL & Advisory Panel on Open Research Software

18 June 2024

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Thank you!

Outline

- Introduction to Open Science NL:
 - Mission and tasks
 - Development of funding instruments
 - Community engagement strategy
- Advisory Panel on Open Research Software
 - Scope and ways of working
 - Activity plan 2024 & 2025
- Q&A

What is Open Science NL?

- Designated national funding programme for Open Science implementation (€20M/year for 10 years)
- Complementary to what academic and research institutions are doing themselves
- Part of the Dutch Research Council - NWO (same rules, framework) but with its own Steering Board

Open Science NL's mission

“ To advance and accelerate Open Science in the Netherlands with the goal of making Open Science the norm. ”

- By providing (temporary) **funding** for projects and initiatives
- By **monitoring** and evaluating progress
- By providing a forum for **exchange** of best practice
- By organising and facilitating **coordination** at a national level

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Development of funding instruments

Development of financial instruments

NPOS agenda provides overall framework

Work Programme

Approved by the Steering Board & based on community consultation at various levels

Financ. instruments

A diverse array of instruments, tailored to specific topics and community needs

Open Science NL
Work programme 2024 -2025

62.5 M EUR
15 Funding instruments

Open Scholarly
Communication

FAIR Data

Open Research
Software

Citizen Science /
Societal Engagement

1

Capacity building

2

Infrastructure

3

Transparent scientific processes

4

Evidence base for Open Science

5

Empowering communities

Financial instruments in the work programme 2024 & 2025 particularly relevant to research software

- Directly related to Open Research Software:
 - Strengthening local and thematic DCCs (€ 15M)
 - Research Software Sustainability Programme (€ 6M)
- Indirectly related to Open Research Software:
 - Open Science Infrastructure Programme (€ 12.5M)
 - Replication Studies Programme (€ 5.2M)
 - Research on Open Science (€ 2.8M)
 - Recognising and Rewarding Open Science (€ 1.4 M)
 - Open Science Meetings (€ 0.6M)

Community engagement strategy

Open Science NL Community Engagement Strategy

Goal: ensure that the needs of the communities are reflected in the OSNL work programme design

How?

- Direct community consultation
- Advisory panels

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Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Scope:

Advisory panels provide **expert guidance and strategic advice** to the programme leaders in developing effective work programmes and funding instruments that reflect community needs and advance the transition to open science.

Out of scope:

- Providing input/guidance on specific funding instruments
- Decisions pertaining to the work of OSNL

Ways of working:

- Members are experts on content or context and they join in their personal capacity
- Appointment for 2 or 3 years
- Advisory panels adhere to NWO's Code Strategy and Policy Advice
- Composition is guided by the NWO's Diversity and inclusion policy
- Meeting twice per year
- Agendas and minutes are published

Activity plans for the panel for 2024 and 2025

- 2024:
 - Meeting in November/December:
 - Discuss community input for the future work programmes
 - Work Programme 2024 and 2025 implementation update
- 2025:
 - Meeting in Q1/Q2:
 - First ideas on how to turn community input into financial instruments
 - Work Programme 2024 and 2025 implementation update
 - Meeting in Q3:
 - Feedback on the draft Work Programme 2026 and 2027

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Questions?